

Milestone: M1.1 - Establishment of Stakeholder Coordination Group

Lead Participant: EAPM

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Due: 31 Oct 2020

Date Of Completion: 25 Nov 2020

Means of Verification

- Stakeholder Event Organised on Oct 21st with the key stakeholders from the Stakeholder representatives
- Number of attendees - 182
 - Full Day conference on consisting of 6 sessions plus closing sessions, where key stakeholder from Working Groups participated
 - [Agenda](#)
 - Stakeholders coordination group composition has been defined (D1.1)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes

Delayed due to the review quality control process, following the meeting

Project participants & others

Work Package Leads, Patient organisations, Clinicians, medical specialists, Academics, Medicines authorities (EU/EMA and national level), HTA bodies, Funders, Industry (Diagnostic, Pharmaceutical, ICT), National Policy/Decision Makers, Infrastructures, EU Joint Actions

Next action steps

Activation of the Stakeholder Coordination Group through content from the WP.

Meeting our deliverables in 2021

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